

УДК 351.82

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.997981

*Husarov K., Researcher of Educational, Scientific and Production center,
National University of Civil Protection of Ukraine, Kharkiv*

INTERNAL MIGRATION PROCESSES IN USA: EXPERIENCE FOR UKRAINE

The article considers the peculiarities of internal migration processes in the United States of America. The principles of public administration regarding resettlement of forced displaced persons are defined. Proposed measures to reduce the burden on the labor market and the infrastructure of the receiving regions in Ukraine, taking into account the US experience.

Keywords : *internal migration processes, public administration, labor market, forced migrants.*

У статті розглянуто особливості внутрішніх міграційних процесів у Сполучених Штатах Америки. Визначені принципи державного управління розселенням вимушено переміщених осіб. Запропоновані заходи щодо зменшення навантаження на ринок праці й інфраструктуру регіонів, що приймають переселенців в Україні, урахувуючи досвід США.

Ключові слова: *внутрішні міграційні процеси, державне управління, ринок праці, вимушено переміщенні особи.*

Problem setting. The movement of people within the borders of their own state is an extremely important factor for the economic and social growth of the country. In the past few years, the problem of internal migration processes in Ukraine is becoming particularly relevant. This was caused by the growth of the number of internally displaced persons, which was provoked by the antiterrorist operation in the territory of Donetsk and Lugansk regions, as well as the annexation of the Crimean peninsula. The number of internally displaced persons is 10 times greater than that of people who have moved abroad.

At the same time, forced migrants seek large metropolises, such as Kiev, Kharkov, Odessa, Dnipro. This causes over-supply in the labor market in these regions. The United States of America has a wealth of experience in the field of internal migration. This is due to both high mobility among US residents and natural emergency situations that lead to forced relocations within the country.

Recent research and publication analysis. Many foreign scientists have been engaged in the study of internal migration processes in the United States of America. The most significant contribution on this issue was made by such scientists as Raven Molloy, Christopher L. Smith, Abigail Wozniak.

The issues of internal migration processes in general were dealt with by such scientists as O.A. Malinovskaya, O.A. Poznyak, O.V. Kupets, N.V. Mkrtchyan, O.D. Vorobyeva, A.V. Topilin, V. Groppo, J. Devind, J. Holdaway and others. However, it should be noted that improving the state management of internal migration processes in Ukraine requires additional research.

Paper objective. The purpose of this article is to study the peculiarities of internal migration processes in the United States of America, as well as highlight some features of state migration management for their application in Ukraine.

Paper main body. The modern American nation is a young multiethnic formation. It has developed in the process of long cultural, economic, social and domestic interaction. There was a mixture and assimilation of descendants of people of different ethnic origins. In the US population, all three major races of mankind are represented: Mongoloid, European, Negroid.

The majority of US residents are white Americans from the British Isles. The main percentage of them live in the states of Vermont, Maine, New Hampshire, West Virginia, Iowa, Idaho, Wyoming, Minnesota, North Dakota. Self-identified German Americans, according to the census accounted for 17.1% of the population or 50,000,000 people. These immigrants from Germany or Alsace form the largest group, which includes 1/3 of the German diaspora in the world. Latin Americans of European descent also belong to white Americans. The racial and ethnic minority in the country is represented by African-Americans from West and Central Africa. They

are the descendants of the enslaved Negroes. It should be noted that immigrants from Africa, the Caribbean, Central and South America can identify themselves with this term.

The approximate racial composition of the US population is as follows:

- White population from different regions - 75%;
- African Americans - 12.5%;
- Americans of Asian descent – 4 %;
- Indigenous people, including Alaska residents - 0.8%;
- Mixed and transitional races - 7.5%;
- Residents of the Hawaiian Islands – 0.2%. [1]

The distribution of the population on the territory of the country is connected with the geography of cities, the number of which is growing rapidly. For example, in the middle of the last century, urban agglomerations in the country were 170, and in the late 80's there were about 300 of them. Interestingly, there are only 8 cities-millionaires in the country. In millionaires belong to New York, Chicago, Los Angeles , Houston, Philadelphia, Detroit, Dallas, San Diego. And the agglomeration of millionaires is 35. This is indicated by the fact that America is a country of urban agglomerations and the bulk of the population, about 80%, lives in cities. Since the 50's, the country has seen the emergence of large municipal formations, known as megacities.

Currently, there are three largest megalopolises in the country:

- the Northeast, stretching from Boston to Washington;
- Near-lake - located between Chicago and Pittsburgh;
- Californian - is located between San Francisco and San Diego.

As for the rural population, it prefers to live on separate farms. The conditions and way of life of rural residents are not much different from the townspeople. In the south-east of the country, rural settlements are more compact and numerous. The population of the country is unevenly distributed, and its average density is 23 people per square kilometer. Excluding remote Alaska, density increases to 30 people per square kilometer [2].

The American population density is about 10 times lower than the European density. In the world ranking on density, the United States is on the 18th place. The most densely populated northeastern regions of the country, where the population density reaches 100 people per square kilometer. Mountainous and agrarian regions have a lower density - from 2-11 people per square kilometer. In Alaska, the population density is minimal.

The general picture of population density can be represented as follows:

- In the states of the Atlantic coast, the population density is maximal;
- The minimum density is characteristic for mountain states;
- The density of the Pacific coast increases again.

The American nation is very mobile, and this is manifested in the fact that every 5th American changes his place of residence every year, moving from one state to another. The settlers are moving in all directions, although here one can note the tendency to move to the West for a long time. California was especially attractive, so its population increased by 21.2 million people and the share in the population of the country increased from 3 to 10%. The western direction of migration coincided with the displacement of the population from the southern states to the North of the USA [3]. This direction of migration was associated with the outflow of the Negro population from the rural districts of the South to the large northern cities. For many decades, the southern states had a negative migration balance, with the exception of Florida with a favorable climate.

The decline in the population growth rate in the 1970s has also markedly changed the trend of internal migration - the flow of migrants to California has dramatically decreased, and the movement from the northern states to the southern ones has increased. If in the 50 years the population of the northern and southern states had a ratio of 55:45, then in 1990 this ratio changed by 45:55. The fastest growing population of three states - California, Texas, Florida [4].

In turn, periodically there are the compelled migrants from the regions, which combine from extraordinary incidents of a natural character. These are all kinds of hurricanes, floods, forest fires. It should be noted that the state policy is aimed at

resettlement of internally displaced persons in those regions where there is a need for labor, and not in the closest to the zone of the accident. Certain economic and tax privileges are rendered to the host regions of the forced migrants. Respectively, internal migration is also seen as a way of economic development of the United States.

In Ukraine, this practice is not applied at the moment and is not subject of state regulation. This is provoked by the fact that the majority of forced migrants are inclined to move to the areas located near the place of their previous residence. This concentration of immigrants is a burden for the labor market and the infrastructure of the host regions [5]. It is necessary to take into account that the military events in the Donbass will be a significant factor in the redistribution of the population across Ukraine not only in the short term, but also in the medium term.

In addition, the causes of migration processes in USA are:

- Shift of the productive forces to the South and West of the country, which is connected with the development of the electronic and aerospace industries;
- Migration of pensioners. People of retirement age are attracted in the South by the best natural and climatic conditions, prices for land and housing, lower costs of living. Statistics show that the cities of Las Vegas, Houston, Phoenix, Denver, Orlando, Atlanta turned out to be attractive for migrants.

The largest loss from internal migration was experienced by the Northeast United States. Differences in migration flows exist among representatives of age groups. For example, young people from the age of 20 to 29 come from the northern regions of the country. The reason for the age migration, in this case, is the reduction of economic opportunities.

According to the forecast of specialists until 2025, the negative indicators of migration will be characteristic for the Northeast and the Midwest. The main migration stream will have a southern direction. The largest number of migrants will receive Florida and Texas.

Conclusions. The inhabitants of the United States of America are very prone to internal resettlement. This is instigated by a number of factors, among which:

- socio-economic development of the host regions;
- stagnation in certain regions from which the relocation is carried out;
- natural disasters, etc.

At the same time, in the US socio-economic mechanisms of state administration are applied to internally displaced persons, as well as to the regions that receive them. Considering the situation in Ukraine, the following public management activities are proposed:

- when settling forced migrant, take into account the needs of the regions in certain specialists;
- provide tax incentives to the receiving regions, with a view to their economic development.

References

1. Molloy, R., Smith, C. L. and Wozniak, A. "Internal Migration in the United States." *Journal of Economic Perspectives* 25 (3) (2011): 173-96. Print.
2. Molloy, R., Smith, C. L. and Wozniak, A. K. *Declining migration within the US: The role of the labor market* (No. w20065). National Bureau of Economic Research, 2014. Print.
3. Jauer, J., Liebig, T., Martin, J. P. and Puhani, P. A. *Migration as an adjustment mechanism in the crisis? A comparison of Europe and the United States*, 2014. Print.
4. Zabel, J. E. "Migration, housing market, and labor market responses to employment shocks." *Journal of Urban Economics*, 72 (2) (2012): 267-284. Print.
5. Ukraine. Interdepartmental Coordination Headquarters. *898095 people were displaced from the temporarily occupied territory*. 10 July 2015. Web. <http://www.kmu.gov.ua/control/uk/publish/articleart_id=248316491&cat_id=248817973>.

